

Funded by
the European Union

This article has been submitted to IGARSS 2024

Statistical Inference Based on Sentinel-2 and in Situ NDVI Measurements Using Monte Carlo Sampling

Mihai Ivanovici¹ Corneliu Florea^{1,2} Artur Kazak¹

¹Electronics and Computers,

Transilvania University of Brasov, Brasov, Romania

²National University of Science and Technology Politehnica, Bucharest, Romania

{mihai.ivanovici, artur.kazak}@unitbv.ro

cflorea@upb.ro

Abstract

NDVI is the most used vegetation index for the monitoring of vegetation status of agricultural crops. In situ measurements are generally used for the validation of remote sensing data. However, due to various factors, the remotely sensed data may not completely agree with in situ acquired data. We computed NDVI based on Sentinel-2 data and performed in situ NDVI measurements on a specific agricultural area. We used Monte Carlo sampling for the estimation of the distribution of coincidence values, assuming either statistical independence and correlation of data. Based on the estimated distribution, we computed the probability that NDVI falls in two intervals of interest, based on a threshold widely used for the interpretation of the NDVI values.

1 Introduction

Vegetation indices are computed based on various wavelengths acquired by optical remote sensing devices. They are very useful to quantify various aspects related to agricultural crops, like vegetation health status or development stage, canopy abundance and photosynthetic activity. Since they target different aspects of vegetation growth, including their characteristics related to species or physiological conditions, a plethora of vegetation indices have been proposed [1], for the purpose of capturing both intrinsic and extrinsic characteristics of plants. The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) is the most used vegetation index, that offers insights into various aspects of plant health and density. NDVI is computed using the spectral reflectance values of the red (RED) and near-infrared (NIR) spectral bands, as:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - RED}{NIR + RED} \quad (1)$$

, its range being from -1 to +1. By examining the NDVI values makes it possible to identify regions characterized by well-developed, stressed or dead vegetation, as described in Table 1.

NDVI	interpretation
[-1, 0]	water/artificial surface
[0,0.33]	dried/dead/underdevelopped
[0.33, 0.66]	moderately healthy/developped
[0.66, 1]	very healthy/developped

Table 1: NDVI range and interpretation.

NDVI can be computed based on the multi-spectral data provided the Sentinel-2 satellite, by selecting B4 and B8 bands for RED and NIR, respectively [2] or by using hyper-spectral data provided by various missions, like PRISMA [3]. The in situ NDVI measurements can be performed using various existing instruments, specifically designed for the task. Usually, in situ data is used for the validation of the remotely-sensed data, or even the calibration of the remote sensing instruments. However, in our experiments, we noticed a difference both in average and variability between the NDVI computed based on remotely-sensed data and the NDVI acquired by in situ measurements.

In this article we address the issue of mismatch between the remotely-sensed data and the in situ acquired data. We propose a statistical inference approach, based on the Monte Carlo sampling of the two distribution data, in order to infer a distribution of the coincidences in the initial data. Monte Carlo simulation is used when actual measurements are hard or too costly and previous applications in agriculture include crop simulation [4], energy consumption [5]; in the context of NDVI based measurements, Monte Carlo simulation has been used inside a Markov chain to fill in time series for future prediction [6].

In this paper, we considered two working scenarios: the two data sets are statistically (i) independent and (ii) correlated. Based on the estimated distribution and given the unanimously-accepted thresholds for the interpretation of the NDVI values, we compute the probabilities of making the correct decision from an end-user point of view.

2 Approach

2.1 Data

We used two types of data, corresponding to the same location on Earth: remotely-sensed data provided by the Sentinel-2 satellite (at 10m spatial resolution) and in-situ measurements; both have been acquired and performed on the same date - September 22nd, 2023. In Figure 1 we show the RGB color composite of the Sentinel-2 image and the corresponding NDVI map. The field where the in situ measurements were performed is marked as a red polygon. The NDVI map was produced by using the ESA SNAP application and the Sentinel-2 NDVI specific color palette. One may notice that the data is partially affected by clouds, thus we used only the pixels that are not covered by clouds.

Figure 1: Sentinel-2 data: RGB color composite (left) and corresponding NDVI map (right).

The in situ measurements were performed using a FieldScout NDVI meter, that directly measures and displays NDVI values by considering the spectral reflectance values on the 700 nm and 840 nm wavelengths.

In Table 2 we show for the two data sets, the mean and standard deviation. As one can notice, there is a considerable disagreement between the two sources of data, both in terms of the mean and standard deviation. The smaller deviation of in situ measurement can be explained by the more simple and robust process, compared to the high complexity of the satellite instrument and the interference from a multitude of factors for remote sensing (the presence of clouds may be one of the reasons for the higher variability of the Sentinel-2 data compared to the in situ measure-

ments). The smaller deviation also suggest that in situ measurements are more reliable. However, based solely on the two values for the mean NDVI, the decision regarding the interpretation, with respect to the 0.33 threshold, simply cannot be made.

NDVI	mean	standard deviation
Sentinel-2	0.3555	0.0526
in situ	0.3153	0.0155

Table 2: NDVI mismatch between the remotely-sensed data and in situ measurements.

In order to analyse the implication of various factors for the decision, we resort to statistical simulation.

2.2 Monte Carlo sampling

In this section we describe the Monte Carlo simulation procedure, which is used to delve into the causality relation between the two types of data. The simulation justification is twofold. From a practical point of view, it replaces the costly measurements. From an algorithmic perspective, it avoids inverting the probability density function of two dimensional correlated Gaussian variables. Regarding the later, the two measurements are modelled by two random variables (RV) which, individually were choose to be Gaussian (extrapolated from Burr and LogNormal distributions), and when there is a relation (i.e. dependency) between them, requires that the pair to be drawn from a two dimensional Gaussian probability density function. With respect to the latter, since it has no analytical cumulative density function is hard to be sampled for 1 dimension and much harder for multi-dimensional and correlated.

Monte Carlo sampling (MCS) methods are a broad set of statistical algorithms based on repeated random sampling to approximate probability density function (pdf) from instances and without computing the actual distribution. [7]. In our framework, we assume \mathcal{A} to be the random variable modelling the remote-sensed data and \mathcal{B} the RV modelling in situ measurements. The two form a vector which is described a two-dimensional Gaussian (normal):

$$[\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}]^T \sim P_{\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}}(x, y) = \mathcal{N}(x, y; \mu_1, \mu_2, \sigma_1^2, \sigma_2^2, \rho) \quad (2)$$

where μ_1, μ_2 forms the mean vector, $\sigma_1^2 \sigma_2^2$ are the variances of the two random variables while ρ is the Pearson correlation coefficient between \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} . We recall that, being Gaussian, if $\rho = 0$, then $P_{\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}}(x, y) = P_{\mathcal{A}}(x)P_{\mathcal{B}}(y)$.

In this case, the MCS implementation uses the Metropolis-Hasting principles [8] and has the following main steps:

- Start from a pair of randomly drawn values $x_0 \sim \mathcal{N}(x; \mu_1, \sigma_1^2)$ and respectively $y_0 \sim \mathcal{N}(y; \mu_2, \sigma_2^2)$;
- At a step i :
 - Propose new samples $x_i^p = x_{i-1} + \xi$ and $y_i^p = y_{i-1} + \eta$, where ξ and η are uniform random variables:

$$\begin{aligned} P_\xi(u) &\sim \mathcal{U}\left(-\frac{\sigma_1}{2}; \frac{\sigma_1}{2}\right) \\ P_\eta(u) &\sim \mathcal{U}\left(-\frac{\sigma_2}{2}; \frac{\sigma_2}{2}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

- Compute the probability of transition:

$$\pi_i = \frac{P_{\mathcal{A},\mathcal{B}}(x_i^p, y_i^p)}{P_{\mathcal{A},\mathcal{B}}(x_{i-1}, y_{i-1})} \quad (4)$$

- If $\pi_i > u \sim \mathcal{U}(0; 1)$ then $[x_i, y_i] = [x_i^p, y_i^p]$ else $[x_i, y_i] = [x_{i-1}, y_{i-1}]$
- Stop after a number of steps (e.g. 10000).

The cases "i" in which x_i and y_i agree, are used to estimate the NDVI probability.

3 Results

In Figure 2 we show the best fitted known distributions: Burr for the Sentinel-2 data and Log-Normal for the in situ data, exhibiting the slight disagreement between the remotely-sensed data and in situ measurement data. One can notice that the NDVI meter provided relatively a slim distribution (in blue), while the Sentinel-2 provided relatively spread values (in red). However, both data sources are calibrated and trustable, consequently one has to find a way to mitigate the slight discrepancy between the two data.

Assuming that the two data sets are statistically independent, we performed a Monte Carlo simulation in order to determine the probability density of the coincidences between the two data sets. After performing the statistical inference using the Monte Carlo sampling previously described, we obtained the histogram shown in Figure 3 together with its envelope computed using the kernel density estimation (KDE) function available in Matlab.

Based on the MCS-determined new distribution, we computed the following two probabilities: $P_{NDVI \in [0, 0.33]} = 0.773$ and $P_{NDVI \in [0.33, 0.66]} = 0.227$, for a certain instance of the simulation. Consequently, one can make the decision that the vegetation is dead and no further treatment should be applied. Based on the in situ observation, this would be the correct decision,

Figure 2: Estimated NDVI distributions for the remotely-sensed and in-situ data.

given that at the date of data acquisition, the experimental wheat field was harvested already.

Assuming the independence hypothesis may not be true, as one can consider that the remotely-sensed data includes somehow the in situ measured data, therefore one may assume a certain correlation and causation between the two data sets. After performing the Monte Carlo simulation by considering the pair of the two Gaussian random variables, for various values of the correlation coefficient ρ , we obtained the results in Figure 4. One can notice that, as ρ increases, the histogram is translated to lower values and the variance of data is diminishing.

Based on the estimated distributions in Figure 4, we computed the probabilities that NDVI belongs to intervals of interest: $[0,0.33]$ and $[0.33,0.66]$ respectively and we present the results in Table 3. The simulation results show that, as expected, the probability $P_{NDVI \in [0,0.33]}$ decreases with ρ , however it leads to the same decision, that the vegetation is dead (which corresponds to the in field real situation).

Increasing the correlation between them means to assume that the relation between them is stronger, with the possibility of determining a simple linear transformation between the two random variables. In that case, the pair of random variables is regressed to a single variable and the decision from in situ dominates, due to the smaller deviation.

Figure 3: Histogram and KDE of NDVI values obtained by Monte Carlo sampling of the two initial data sets (assuming the statistical independence).

4 Conclusion

We performed the analysis of NDVI corresponding to an experimental field where the wheat crops was already harvested at the end of September 2023. We compared two sets of data for the NDVI: remotely-sensed multi-spectral data provided by the Sentinel-2 satellite and in situ measurement data acquired with a portable NDVI meter. As expected, there is a slight discrepancy between the data, the remotely-sensed one exhibiting a slightly higher variability, as well as a shift of the mean. We proposed a statistical inference approach based on Monte Carlo sampling for the harmonization of the two data sets. We performed the simulation in two scenarios: (i) the two data sets are statistically-independent and (ii) there is an unknown statistical correlation between the two data sets. Based on the newly-determined data distribution, we computed the probabilities that the NDVI values fall below or above a given threshold. Considering the threshold of 0.33, the results show that the correct decision is made. As future work, we plan to further investigate the causality between the remotely-sensed data and the in situ measured data, for various agricultural crops.

Figure 4: KDEs of NDVI values obtained by Monte Carlo sampling of the two initial data sets (assuming the statistical correlation).

ρ	$P_{NDVI \in [0,0.33]}$	$P_{NDVI \in [0.33,0.66]}$
1.0	0.998	0.0014
0.9	0.989	0.0107
0.75	0.969	0.0304
0.5	0.849	0.1506
0.25	0.827	0.1722
0.1	0.809	0.1905
0.01	0.750	0.2491

Table 3: The Monte Carlo simulation results.

Acknowledgments

Funded by the European Union. The AI4AGRI project entitled “Romanian Excellence Center on Artificial Intelligence on Earth Observation Data for Agriculture” received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement no. 101079136.

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The authors would like to thank our collaborators and project partners

from the National Institute of Research and Development for Potato and Sugar Beet, Brasov, Romania for their support in performing the in-situ measurements.

References

- [1] Abdou Bannari, Daniel Morin, F Bonn, and A.R. Huete, “A review of vegetation indices,” *Remote sensing reviews*, vol. 13, no. 1-2, pp. 95–120, 1995.
- [2] Rosa Lasaponara, Nicodemo Abate, Carmen Fattore, Angelo Aromando, Gianfranco Cardettini, and Marco Di Fonzo, “On the use of sentinel-2 ndvi time series and google earth engine to detect land-use/land-cover changes in fire-affected areas,” *Remote Sensing*, vol. 14, no. 19, pp. 4723, 2022.
- [3] Ioana Cristina Plajer, Alexandra Baicoianu, Luciana Majercsik, and Mihai Ivanovici, “Ndvi computation from hyperspectral images,” in *13th Workshop on Hyperspectral Imaging and Signal Processing: Evolution in Remote Sensing (WHISPERS)*, 2023, pp. 1–4.
- [4] Roberto Confalonieri, “Monte carlo based sensitivity analysis of two crop simulators and considerations on model balance,” *European Journal of Agronomy*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 89–93, 2010.
- [5] Mostafa Mardani Najafabadi and Morteza Taki, “Robust data envelopment analysis with monte carlo simulation model for optimization the energy consumption in agriculture,” *Energy Sources, Part A: Recovery, Utilization, and Environmental Effects*, pp. 1–15, 2020.
- [6] Fernando Sedano, Pieter Kempeneers, and George Hurtt, “A kalman filter-based method to generate continuous time series of medium-resolution ndvi images,” *Remote Sensing*, vol. 6, no. 12, pp. 12381–12408, 2014.
- [7] Christian Robert and George Casella, *Monte Carlo Statistical Methods*, Springer Science & Business Media, 2013.
- [8] Siddhartha Chib and Edward Greenberg, “Understanding the metropolis-hastings algorithm,” *The american statistician*, vol. 49, no. 4, pp. 327–335, 1995.